

Numerical Study of Viscoelastic Soil Effects in Seismic Metamaterials

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Abstract—This work studies how a deviatoric generalized Maxwell soil response modifies seismic metamaterial dispersion. Finite-element eigenfrequency simulations show that stiffness changes and dynamic stiffening shift modal branches at higher frequency values. The results indicate that seismic metamaterial design should account for realistic soil inelasticity, since the intended functionality may change.

Keywords— seismic metamaterials, viscoelasticity, band gaps, finite element modelling, eigenfrequency analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Seismic metamaterials use periodic inclusions, resonators, or structured soil domains to attenuate surface waves through scattering and band-gap formation [1], [2]. Most numerical studies assume an ideal elastic soil, although realistic seismic loading can involve damping and other inelastic effects. This work enriches the non-hierarchical unit-cell model of Miniaci *et al.* [3] by adding a dissipative generalized-Maxwell soil response. It is shown that accounting for dissipative effects results in high deviation from the intended seismic metamaterial functionality, a fact that suggests that these must be designed with care for real-case scenarios.

II. METHODS

The employed finite-element model follows that reported in Miniaci *et al.* [3]. The soil height was set to $H = \min(L_{\max}, 8\lambda)$, with $L_{\max} = 1000$ m, reducing the original computational costs while keeping the eigenfrequency problem solvable. This setup was used to isolate the effects of deviatoric viscoelasticity and increased soil stiffness.

TABLE I
ELASTIC MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND REFERENCE SPEEDS.

Case	E MPa	ρ kg/m ³	ν	c_S m/s	c_L m/s	c_R m/s
LowE	20	1800	0.30	65.4	122.3	60.6
HighE	320	1900	0.33	251.6	499.5	234.3

The c_S , c_L , and c_R references are plotted as $f = ck_x/(2\pi)$ over $k^* = k_x/(\pi/a)$ and they are reference slopes.

For the viscoelastic cases, one Maxwell branch was introduced with

$$G_0 = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}, \quad G_1 = rG_0, \quad \tau_1 = \frac{1}{2\pi f_{relax}}, \quad (1)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, G_0 is the instantaneous shear modulus, G_1 is the shear modulus of

the Maxwell branch, $r = G_1/G_0$, and τ_1 is the characteristic relaxation time of that branch. In the absence of rheological data, $r = 0.3$ was chosen as a moderate contrast: a preliminary sweep showed nearly linear modal sensitivity, with a visible frequency shift already at this value. The relaxation frequency, f_{relax} , was similarly set to 12 Hz, placing the Maxwell transition within the HighE modal window, whose first mode is near 10 Hz. It must be noted that only the deviatoric response is dissipative, while the volumetric response remains elastic. The corresponding shear modulus is:

$$G^*(\omega) = G_0 + \frac{G_1 i\omega\tau_1}{1 + i\omega\tau_1}. \quad (2)$$

Thus $G^* \approx G_0$ at low frequencies, and $G^* \rightarrow G_0 + G_1$ at high frequencies, so the model introduces both damping and dynamic stiffening.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With respect to Miniaci *et al.* [3], the PML was here replaced with a low-reflecting boundary, and the use of the capped wavelength-scaled height preserves the qualitative modal structure of the reference simulation, as shown in Fig. 1(a-b). Thus, it yields the same result of the reference, though saving computational time; this is a validation step, not the main physical result.

TABLE II
PROGRESSIVE MODELLING CHANGES AND OBSERVED TRENDS.

Case	Main observation
Reference elastic No PML	Baseline elastic modal structure. Similar branches; lower computational time than Ref.
LowE viscoelastic	Modest upward shift from frequency-dependent shear stiffness.
HighE elastic	Shift from about 2.5–6 Hz to about 10–25 Hz.
HighE viscoelastic	Preserved structure with a moderate shift for $r = 0.3$, $f_{relax} = 12$ Hz.

Adding viscoelasticity to the LowE model modestly shifts the modal branches upward, consistent with the high-frequency Maxwell limit where the effective shear stiffness approaches $G_0 + G_1$. Increasing elastic stiffness has a stronger effect: the HighE elastic case shifts the spectrum from about 2.5–6 Hz to 10–25 Hz. In the viscoelastic case, $f_{relax} = 12$ Hz avoids a fully high-frequency asymptotic response, while

Fig. 1. Eigenfrequency results and selected HighE viscoelastic mode shapes, filtered based on the p -value. Panel (a) reports the reference elastic case; panels (b,c) use $H = \min(L_{\max}, 8\lambda)$, $L_{\max} = 1000$ m. Panel (c) uses $r = 0.3$ and $f_{\text{relax}} = 12$ Hz. Panels (d)–(g) show representative modes at X .

$r = 0.3$ gives a moderate visible deviation from the elastic diagram, Fig. 1(c). Table II separates numerical validation from stiffness and viscoelastic effects.

Stronger preliminary viscoelastic cases showed a small splitting of two modes nearly coincident in elastic simulations. This may reflect damping-induced lifting of an accidental degeneracy, although mesh/solver convergence is needed before interpreting its magnitude quantitatively.

The modal shapes in Fig. 1(d)–(g) were extracted at $k = 2$, i.e., at X along Γ – X . The deformation is localized near the surface, with out-of-plane and mixed character comparable to the surface-mode shapes reported in Miniaci *et al.* [3]. The frequency range is shifted upward by the HighE material and Maxwell-branch stiffening.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed simplified model shows the same behavior of Miniaci *et al.* [3]: the same general band-gap behavior and distinction between strongly excited, mainly out-of-plane SAW-type modes and weakly excited modes remain. In the HighE configuration, these features shift upward due to increased stiffness and Maxwell-branch dynamic stiffening. Thus, higher-order effects must be considered with due care for the faithful design of seismic metamaterials. Future works will consider plasticity and dissipative effects.

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